

Cultural Game Jam Kit

Capacity Building

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EPIC-WE

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What This Kit Does

In the first section, the what, why, and how, along with practical steps to develop, plan, and structure Cultural Game Jams for Capacity Building is detailed.

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Outcomes and Advantages

Running Capacity Building workshops as Cultural Game Jams enables particular outcomes and advantages, which are highlighted in this section, along with next steps for facilitators and participants.

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Secret Missions

Developed through the [EPIC-WE project](#) and tested during the EPIC-WE Lecacies Event in February 2026, the Secret Missions approach to Capacity Building is introduced and explained in this section as a novel format for experiencing and innovating tangible and intangible cultural heritage through co-creation.

04

Secret Envelopes 1-4

This section provides a step-by-step guide to utilising the Secret Missions format, made tangible through four different envelopes provided to the participants. It follows the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam phases - Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create, along with tools, approaches, and methods.

05

Supplementary Resources

The last section links to relevant resources, materials, and methods that can be integrated in and support Cultural Game Jams for Capacity Building.

Section 1

What this Kit does?

This kit provides a structured yet flexible methodology for exploring and applying **Cultural Game Jams** as a capacity-building format. It translates the established CGJ phases into a model that helps teams, educators, cultural workers, and communities develop:

- Creative experiences and outputs
- Collaborative practices
- Cultural awareness and remixing
- Value-sensitive reflection
- Prototyping and experimentation skills

The kit can be used to train staff, support organisational development, or empower participants with new experiences through hands-on cultural creation, or as a playful exploring of games, culture, values, and citizenship.

What, Why, How

What is a Capacity-Building Cultural Game Jam?

A facilitated process where participants learn together by co-creating cultural game concepts and prototypes. The focus is not on producing a polished game, but on developing shared skills, prototypes, and understandings through playful, creative, and cultural work.

Why use CGJs for Capacity Building?

Because CGJs engage people in collaboration, experimentation, and cultural reflection. They enable low-stakes creativity and deep cross-disciplinary engagement. Moreover, they support rapid skill uptake and hands-on application of cultural and value-based insights, in a mutual learning space for organisational development

How does it work?

Through four structured mini-phases of Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create, each with targeted methods that build specific capacities: ideation, conceptual thinking, prototyping, reflection, and cultural engagement.

Capacity Building Formats and Insights

These capacity-building CGJs and workshops introduce cultural game jams, culture- and value-sensitive game-making, and games through and for culture as an innovative way to empower young people as co-creators of European culture and shapers of their own futures in society, cultural institutions, and creative industries.

Objectives

- Equip participants with the knowledge to organise cultural game jams
- Build capacity across cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education
- Foster understanding of the quadruple helix ecosystem approach
- Develop skills in youth engagement and cultural participation methods
- Gain insights into empowered participation in cultural heritage

Target Audience

- Cultural heritage institutions (CHIs)
- Creative industries (CIs)
- Higher education institutions (HEIs)
- Youth organisations and facilitators
- Game development professionals interested in cultural application

Learn More

The approach highlighted here is based on *Secret Missions*, a joyful and playful way to collaborate through culture in new ways, though there are multiple ways to organise a capacity-building workshop inspired by cross-sector innovation, cultural game-making, and cultural game jams.

In [EPIC-WE](#), the “EPIC-WE Capacity Building Workshops & Game Exhibitions Guidelines” detail practical and technical requirements for running such workshops to support cultural and value-sensitive innovation.

Capacity Building Approaches and Outcomes

In capacity-building formats, cultural game jams, culture- and value-sensitive game-making, and games *through* and *for* culture are approached as innovative ways to empower young people as co-creators of European culture and as shapers of their own futures in society, cultural institutions, and creative industries.

Games through and for Culture are the tangible outcomes of Cultural Game Jams, showcasing the innovative conceptualisation of *games in culture*. **Games through culture** use game-making as a new form of culture-making by using cultural heritage as game-making material to create alternative cultural worlds within the medium of games. **Games for culture** engage youth as citizens and highlight their cultural and societal reflections, engagements or transformations of their cultural world.

Suggested Structures: 1 Hour Capacity-Building

Minutes 0-10:

- EPIC-WE Overview
- Workshop Objectives and Expectations
- Icebreaker & Introductions

Minutes 10-25: Core Methodology

- Quadruple helix ecosystems and interactive mapping exercise
- Cultural game jam process walkthrough with detailed phases
- Case studies from successful EPIC-WE implementations
- Q&A session on methodology clarifications

Minutes 25-45: Hands-on Planning Workshop

- Group formation (4-5 participants each, mixed sector backgrounds)
- Detailed cultural game jam scenario design exercise:
 - Target audience identification and youth engagement strategies
 - Local cultural heritage resource mapping and selection
 - Partnership identification and role allocation
 - Timeline development (pre-jam, jam event, post-jam activities)
 - Budget considerations and resource requirements
 - Risk assessment and mitigation strategies
 - Problem-solving session on common implementation challenge

Minutes 45-55: presentations & peer learning

- 5 groups present their game jam concepts (2 minutes each)
- Peer feedback and suggestions from other participants
- Network building and partnership opportunity discussions

Minutes 55-60: next steps & closing

- Individual commitment setting and next steps planning
- Support implementation pathway
- Feedback collection and evaluation
 - Distribution of complete digital resources, toolkits, and contact

Read more
about capacity-
building events
in EPIC-WE

Suggested Structures: Secret Mission Workshop

The **Secret Mission Workshop Format** was created and tested during the **EPIC-WE Legacies Event in Aarhus, Denmark**.

The overarching aim and objectives are to facilitate a rapid (3-6 hours) Cultural Game Jam experience that includes all the EPIC phases, approaches, and methods from the Cultural Game Jam Kit, adapted for a joyful, cross-sector capacity-building experience in a shorter timeframe.

Here, you will have the opportunity to co-create games for/through culture across sectors and disciplines, experience game-making as culture-making, and engage with both cultural heritage and EU values. Through this workshop format, the aim is to tangibly experience and create the foundation for inviting and empowering youth to connect with cultural heritage in new ways and to participate in the interpretation, reconfiguration, and expression of culture.

As a facilitator, use the following as a suggested guide towards a capacity-building Cultural Game Jam, where each phase is a secret mission that guides the participants through the processes. For further inspiration, see the **developed game prototypes** in EPIC-WE, along with the **Featured Games** (that are curated and further developed prototypes).

CGJ Kit
Capacity
Building:
Outcomes &
Advantages

Outcomes of a Capacity-Building CGJ

A Capacity-Building Cultural Game Jam develops people and organisations through hands-on collaboration, cultural reflection and expression, and rapid experimentation. While prototypes emerge, the core impact lies in the capacities that participants strengthen, experience and carry forward:

Creative cultural confidence and experiments

Working in a playful, low-risk environment enables creative experimentation with cultural heritage and value-sensitive design

Cross-sector innovation & communication

Co-creating across disciplines and sectors leads to new meetings in the middle, as a dynamic, small-scale QH Cultural Hub, enabling cultural and cross-sector innovation while developing cultural-creative skills.

In-depth work with cultural heritage & values

Participants learn to interpret and approach cultural heritage collections and artefacts through value-sensitive processes and to connect them to societal challenges.

Cross-disciplinary collaboration experience

Participants explore and combine diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and expertise *through game-making as a form of culture-making.*

The jam strengthens a collaborative way of working by offering teams a shared experience of **exploring and solving cultural-creative problems together through game-making.**

Through structured phases, groups develop a common framework and vocabulary across sectors for discussing creativity, cultural heritage, values, and prototyping. As a straightforward toolkit to support cultural innovation, it enables creative methods that can be used beyond the jam, for idea development, strategy discussions, or teaching, leading to empowered participation in and through cultural heritage.

Advantages of Using CGJs for Capacity Building

Cultural Game Jams are a uniquely innovative approach to capacity building, combining creativity, culture, citizenship, value-sensitive design, and diverse collaboration in an immersive, energising format where participants experience game-making as culture-making first hand.

Key Advantages

Game-making as culture-making

Creating games becomes a way to produce new cultural narratives, perspectives, and roles, supporting both “games for culture” (games as imaginative, mediating tools for cultural and societal issues) and “games through culture” (games that reinterpret and express cultural heritage).

Builds capacity while generating exploratory prototypes

Teams practice ideation, cultural analysis, and prototyping, while also producing early concepts that can feed into future cross-sector projects.

Cross-sector innovation in practice

Participants from cultural heritage, higher education, youth and civic society, and creative industries collaborate on equal footing, using the jam format to meet in the middle as a cultural hub and develop ideas together.

Creating an EPIC WE

In the CGJ, participants are coming together in small-scale Cultural Hubs - as explained and framed in the “Establishing Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs”, enabling a creative moment of EPIC togetherness across worlds.

Read more
about the
impact of CGJs -
across sectors.

The End: Design, Play, Repeat

To conclude the jam, participants reflect on how their new skills, methods, and insights can be carried forward into everyday practice.

Capacity Pathways

Participants consider how the capacities they developed — creative confidence and experimentation, cultural heritage interpretation and ideation, cross-sector innovation and inquiry, game-making as culture-making, and vibrant new ideas — can support their ongoing work in teaching, community projects, cultural development, organisational innovation, or research.

Next Steps & Integration

Organisations can keep the momentum alive by introducing small, repeatable practices such as:

- Weekly micro-jams for ideation or solving small challenges
- Cultural reflection sessions using artworks or value prompts
- Prototyping Fridays for testing ideas quickly
- Cross-sector task forces applying jam methods to real cultural-creative and value-sensitive problems

Wrap-Up

Capacity isn't built in a single jam — this kit is a part of sparking a lasting culture of experimentation, collaboration, and cultural engagement. Together with the other EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kits, Capacity Building can be approached and experienced differently: as ways of knowing and creating through cultural heritage, across diverse sectors and worlds, with game-making as an approach for cultural innovation, and as an approach to enable empowered participation within heritage, values, and games.

Secret Missions

Facilitator's Note:

In the following, the first set of CGJ Phase descriptions is for facilitators, and the second is ready-to-print guides for participants, along with the method cards, value cards, and cultural heritage artefact descriptions.

Introducing the Four Secret-Mission Phases

In this capacity-building version of the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ), the journey unfolds through four sealed envelopes, one for each of the E-P-I-C phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. Each envelope contains a *secret mission* that guides participants step by step, building their skills, engaging culture creatively, and creating collaborative capacity as they progress.

This format turns the CGJ into playful and immersive capacity-building for taking up practices of CGJs, where participants open envelopes to discover new CGJ missions, reflection prompts, and method cards as they go.

The Role of the Facilitator

The facilitator prepares the four envelopes in advance, selecting cultural heritage, values, and CGJ method appropriate to the group. Their task is to:

- Curate and assemble the materials for each phase
- “Trigger” the opening of envelopes at the right moment
- Hold the narrative frame of the secret-mission progression towards creating a game through/for culture
- Support reflection and learning throughout the process

While participants move through the missions, the facilitator acts as a quiet orchestrator - setting the stage, ensuring flow, and helping the group get the most out of each CGJ step, without breaking the sense of discovery.

Why Secret Missions?

The format strengthens core capacity-building qualities:

- Focus: One mission within each CGJ phase prevents overload and encourages in-depth engagement with cultural themes, values, and objects.
- Progression: Each envelope builds on the previous, mirroring how CGJs are run, and capacities develop, from cultural exploration to creative play, prototyping, and co-creation of a game through/for culture.
- Shared experience: The unfolding missions give participants hands-on experience with CGJs targeted for capacity building.

1

Envelope 1: EXPERIENCE

Mission: Explore and Reinterpret Culture and Values

This envelope introduces participants to the cultural foundation of the jam. It contains selected cultural heritage objects, value cards, reflective questions, and CGJ method card for Culturestorming. The Experience mission encourages participants to explore cultural heritage deeply and develop a shared analytical language.

Purpose

To help participants become sensitive, creative interpreters of culture and values, forming the basis for collaborative innovation.

Contents (the facilitator selects beforehand)

- Cultural heritage descriptions
- Two European Value Cards
- Culturestorming method card
- Reflection prompts

Process

Participants open the envelope and follow the steps:

1. Explore the artwork and values.
2. Respond to reflective questions that activate cultural, ethical, and interpretive thinking.
3. Conduct a Culturestorming session to produce early cultural ideas.

Outcome

A shared cultural vocabulary and a set of initial, open game ideas shaped by cultural material and EU values.

2

Envelope 2: PLAY

Mission: Strengthen Creative Concept Development through Play

The second envelope introduces a shift from cultural exploration to creative experimentation. It includes 6-8-5 Game Sketching, lightweight sketching materials, and prompts that support divergent thinking and playful exploration.

Purpose

To build capacity for rapid ideation, creative collaboration, and conceptual thinking, without fear of failure.

Contents

- 6-8-5 Game Sketching method card
- Quick-sketch materials (or instructions to use what's available)
- Prompts encouraging unusual, risky, or surprising connections between culture and gameplay
- Optional “wild card” constraints to spark imaginative leaps

Process

1. Each participant creates multiple fast sketches.
2. The group discusses and clusters ideas.
3. Promising concepts are highlighted for their cultural relevance, originality, or learning potential.

Outcome

Multiple emerging ideas and strengthened capacity for experimentation and collective creativity.

3

Envelope 3: IMAGINE

Mission: Turn Ideas into Tangible Prototypes and Shared Decisions

The third envelope supports participants in making early versions of their ideas visible and testable. It contains materials and instructions for building rough mockups, along with prompts that push teams to reflect on design choices.

Purpose

To build skills in low-fidelity prototyping, collaborative decision-making, and embodied exploration of concepts.

Contents

- Rough Mockup method card
- Simple prototyping materials (or instructions for creating them quickly)
- Prompts that guide decisions about cultural meaning, player experience, and interpretive depth

Process

1. Teams choose one or more concepts to prototype.
2. They build rough mockups using paper, objects, or quick roleplay.
3. They evaluate mockups based on how well they embody cultural heritage, values, and player experience.

Outcome

A tangible prototype that supports team alignment and deeper decision-making around cultural, experiential, and gameplay qualities.

4

Envelope 4: CREATE

Mission: Finalise a Playable (Rough) Prototype

The final envelope provides the tools and prompts for transforming mockups into simple playable prototypes. It includes the method card for Playable Prototypes, testing prompts, and instructions for preparing a small exhibition or sharing session.

Purpose

To build the capacity to implement ideas, collaborate across roles, and refine prototypes through feedback and iteration.

Contents

- Playable Prototype method card
- Instructions for building analogue, digital, or hybrid prototypes
- Testing prompts and questions about experience, empowerment, and cultural meaning
- Instructions for a simple expo or sharing round

Process

1. Teams turn their mockups into playable prototypes.
2. They test and refine the experience using the prompts.
3. They share their prototypes with others, reflecting on process, choices, and cultural insights.

Outcome

A simple but playable prototype and strengthened practical skills in implementation, communication, and collaborative innovation.

Secret Envelope 01 Experience

CREATE: Focuses on experiencing and exploring ideas around cultural heritage as material for game-making and on potential connections between cultural heritage and games.

The overarching aim of this phase is to generate initial, very open ideas.

1

Envelope 1: EXPERIENCE GUIDE

Welcome to Phase 1: Your Secret Mission Begins

You are now entering **Experience**, the first step on your Cultural Game Jam journey.

In this phase, your mission is to explore culture, values, and meaning together, and to spark the first ideas that will fuel your game concept later. Inside this envelope, you will find everything you need to begin:

- Cultural heritage artefact to explore
- Two EU Value Cards that offer ethical and societal perspectives
- One method card describing your process (Culturestorming)
- A set of reflection prompts

Your Mission

Explore and Reinterpret Culture and Values

Work collaboratively to interpret the cultural heritage artefact, connect it with the selected values, and generate a wide range of early ideas. Treat this as an open, curious exploration: there are no wrong answers.

How You'll Work

1. Study the cultural heritage artefact and values closely.
2. Use the reflection prompts to guide your discussion.
3. Run the Culturestorming method to create many small ideas quickly.
4. Cluster and share what surprised or inspired you.

Transition Tools

In this phase, the transition tool (Ideation Wheel) is optional. Use it only if you want to explore and capture plural key observations for later.

Culturestorming

In this activity, similar to traditional brainstorming, participants will come up with initial game ideas that blend values, culture, and citizenship. The goal of "culturestorming" is to spark fresh ideas about cultural artefacts and cultural heritage - and to explore different perspectives and themes to deepen our understanding and inspire the creation of meaningful and innovative games.

Suggested Activity Time
20-40 minutes

Experience

Culture

Culturestorming

How

1. Frame a question grounded in culture and the chosen cultural artefact
2. Individually brainstorm 5 ideas in 3 minutes in written form. 1 idea per Post-it.
3. Group ideas into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on your favourite ideas for innovative cultural games.

Reflect

1. What cultural experience do we want the player to have?
2. How do we use culture as material for a game?
3. How can the game capture the essence of the chosen cultural heritage?

What

Pen, post-its, and papers.

Outcome

A number of cultural ideas to move forward with.

Use

Early in the “Experience” phase.

Reference

Secret Envelope 02 Play

PLAY: Here, the focus is on conceptualising ideas generated in the Experience Phase using a method specifically designed for 'toying with ideas'.

The overarching aim of the work and method is to create a game concept.

2

Envelope 2: PLAY GUIDE

Welcome to Phase 2: Time to Experiment, Explore, and Take Creative Risks

Your next secret mission is about creative concept development and novel ideas.

Here, you'll stretch your creativity, sketch fast, and build on each other's thinking. Inside this envelope, you will find:

- The 6-8-5 Game Sketching method card
- Sketching materials or instructions
- Creative prompts and optional constraints to push your thinking

Your Mission

Strengthen Creative Concept Development through Play

Generate as many rough game ideas as you can, quick, messy, imaginative. This is your laboratory phase: experiment boldly and let quantity lead you toward unexpected directions.

How You'll Work

1. Each participant sketches multiple cultural game ideas rapidly.
2. Share and discuss the ideas with the group.
3. Identify which ones feel intriguing, surprising, or meaningful.
4. Combine, remix, and adapt the most promising ones.

Transition Tools

In this phase, transition tools are also optional. If helpful, you can seek feedback from peers.

6-8-5 Game Sketching

This brainstorming activity helps designers quickly generate multiple rough ideas. By focusing on rapid and diverse idea creation, the design team explores several potential ideas and concepts rather than seeking the "best" one. The goal is to stimulate creativity and come up with as many ideas for cultural games as possible within a short timeframe.

Suggested Activity Time

20 minutes

Play

Games

6-8-5 Game Sketching

How

1. Draw a piece of paper into a grid of 8 boxes for each participant.
2. The goal is to generate 6-8 rough games for/through culture ideas in 5 minutes.
3. When the time is up, discuss the team's ideas and decide on the most interesting ones - and if there is time, do another round.

Reflect

1. What ideas hold the biggest potential? What makes it unique?
2. What ideas use cultural heritage in the most surprising ways? In the most elegant ways? In juicy ways?
3. What ideas use culture and value in strange ways that will make players talk about them excitingly?

What

Pens and papers, post-its.

Outcome

Multiple novel game ideas.

Use

Early in the 'Play' phase - or again later if more ideas are needed.

Reference

Secret Envelope 03 Imagine

IMAGINE: Here, the focus is on creating a playable mockup to see whether the core game concept actually works as a cultural heritage experience for the game player.

The aim of the method is to focus the work from the previous phase, along with expert feedback, to start iteratively prototyping your playable version of the game/concept.

3

Envelope 3: IMAGINE GUIDE

Welcome to Phase 3: Turn Ideas Into Something Tangible

This secret mission moves you from ideas to tangible prototypes.

You will bring your best concepts to life through quick mockups that help you see, test, and discuss possibilities.

Inside this envelope, you will find:

- The Rough Mockup method card
- Simple materials (or instructions for improvising them)
- Prompts focused on cultural meaning, values, and player experience
- Transition Tools: Playtesting (required)

Your Mission

Turn Ideas into Tangible Prototypes and Shared Decisions

Build rough, low-fidelity mockups that express your game's core ideas.

These mockups are not final, they help you explore, compare, and refine.

How You'll Work

1. Select one or more concepts to develop.
2. Create quick paper mockups, props, or roleplay setups.
3. Use the prompts to reflect: culture, values, experience, interaction.
4. Share your mockups with another group for rapid feedback.

Transition Tools (Integrated)

In this phase, the transition tools are part of the mission:

- Playtesting with another group is required to gather insights for iterative design and development.

Rough Mockup

Rough prototypes help visualise and communicate game design ideas to team members - and spark discussions about the requirements for each feature, mechanism, or interaction.

This method aims to simulate specific game design elements and components to explore how they might function in a complete prototype.

Suggested Activity Time
45-120 minutes

Imagine

Games

Rough Mockup

How

1. The rough mockup helps explain and decide on game ideas.
2. Create a game mockup - built with paper or existing interface elements (e.g., wireframe/UI kits, game engines).
3. Use mockups(s) to visualise ideas - and consider design paths.

Reflect

1. How do we create mockups that capture our work and thinking in the best possible way?
2. What is the best mockup? Should we make more than one?
3. How can we, with our mockup, materialise different ideas that show what is unique about our game when it comes to culture, cultural heritage and values?

What

Interface elements, game engines, paper, etc.

Outcome

A tangible mockup to discuss and decide with.

Use

When a tangible and visual element is needed for decisions and iterations.

Reference

Secret Envelope 04 Create

CREATE: During the Create Phase, the method's aim and application are to help you leverage all your work from previous phases and develop and create the final game, prototype, or concept.

The focus is on finalising the game.

4

Envelope 4: CREATE / INSTRUCTION

Welcome to Phase 4: *Build, Test, and Finalise Your Playable Prototype*. Your final secret mission is to transform your mockup into a playable prototype and prepare it for sharing. This is where your collaborative decisions and new skills come together. Inside this envelope, you will find:

- The Playable Prototype method card
- Instructions for building analogue, digital, or hybrid prototypes
- Testing prompts to refine the experience
- Guidance for preparing your final pitch or micro-expo
- Transition Tools: Log & Pitch (required)

Your Mission

Finalise a Playable (Rough) Prototype

Build a simple but playable version of your game concept; something others can interact with, respond to, and learn from.

How You'll Work

1. Transform your mockup into a playable prototype.
2. Test the prototype, refine it, and clarify its cultural meaning.
3. Use the prompts to strengthen gameplay, values integration, and empowerment.
4. Prepare a final group pitch or mini-exhibition of your prototype.

Transition Tool (Integrated)

Here, the transition tools are fully woven into the phase:

- *Log* captures the development process and key decisions.
- *Pitch* becomes the format for presenting your final game.

Playable Prototypes

This approach focuses on turning ideas and concepts into a playable prototype shaped by the responsibilities of different roles and the categories of games, culture, values, and citizenship.

The playable prototype can be digital, analogue, or hybrid—created with paper, cardboard, browsers, or other mediums. The goal is to move from mockups to interactive games using either physical or digital materials.

Suggested Activity Time

2-6 hours

Create

Games

Playable Prototypes

How

1. The playable prototype might be analogue, digital, or hybrid, translating into different design constraints and considerations.
2. Draw from earlier mockups to make it playable using paper, cardboard, or digital engines. This way, you'll have more time to test and make improvements.

Reflect

1. How can we create a prototype that enables players to interact with and experience the game's core ideas, themes, and purpose?
2. What are the most important elements to make playable?
3. How does the player experience cultural worlds and empowerment in gameplay?

What

Paper or cardboard; game engine, prototyping app

Outcome

A simple but playable prototype imbued by the categories.

Use

When ready to materialise your final game idea.

Reference

Supplementary Resources

See the:

CGJ Kit: Core Framework

CGJ Kit: Expansion Pack

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